

A DYNAMICALLY OPERATED DUAL CFB CaL TAILORED FOR CARBON CAPTURE OF FUTURE IRON & STEEL INDUSTRIES - DEVELOPMENT AND MODEL INVESTIGATION

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Abstract

Instances necessitating the limitation of global warming to a 1.5 °C temperature increase mandate the deployment of carbon dioxide removal technologies [1]. The steel industry presents a formidable challenge due to its substantial global contribution to greenhouse gas emissions [2]. The complexity of emissions abatement in this sector is compounded by the batch-oriented nature of the steelmaking process and the inherent variability in both flue gas flow rates and properties.

Sumitomo SHI FW (SFW) continues its pioneering efforts for the development of carbon capture technologies together with core partners. The special focus of this study is the adaptation of the well-known calcium looping process (CaL) to capture CO₂ from the steelmaking industry, which is a novel application. This study shows the fundamental stages of steel production and identifies the predominant greenhouse gas emission sources associated with it. Furthermore, it presents the steel case-specific conceptual aspects of the CaL pilot facility, which is under engineering phase and will be used for the demonstration of CO₂ capture in steelmaking. Additionally, the study provides modelling principles regarding a 1.5D dynamic simulation tool and offers preliminary simulation results relating to the time-dependent operation of the CFB-CaL process.

The simulations confirm that the dynamic nature of flue gas originating from the steel production process introduces additional complexities in managing the operation of the CaL system. Owing to the interdependence of material and heat capacity flows, specific design solutions are needed to provide sufficient operational flexibility and particular attention is necessary for developing the control strategies.

1. Introduction

Despite recent reductions in the CO₂ intensity of crude steel production, the iron and steel industry remains a significant contributor to global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, accounting for 7% of total emissions and up to 11% of global CO₂ emissions [2]. Each ton of steel produced emits between 1.4 to 1.85 tons of CO₂, emphasizing the pressing need for accelerated efforts to embrace low-carbon alternatives and implement energy-efficient CO₂ capture technologies.

The CFB-CaL process has been largely investigated for several years and found to be one of the most suitable carbon capture (CC) technologies for different CO₂-intensive processes. Fluctuating properties of gases emitted from the iron/steel making processes are calling for extreme transient flexibility from the CC technology. The CFB combustion process has proven its dynamic flexibility in energy production. Hence, CFB-CaL is expected to be well applicable also for the integration with batch-type steel-making processes. In this work, a first-of-a-kind CaL pilot facility with high operational flexibility is designed in collaboration between SFW and SWERIM. The pilot will be connected to the steel mill, and the performance of the capture technology will be demonstrated with fluctuating exhaust gas properties, like CO₂ concentration, gas flow rate, temperature and impurities.

SFW has developed comprehensive dynamic models for the CFB processes in collaboration with LUT over 15 years. Those models are adapted for the CFB CaL processes by LUT and are utilized in this work to investigate the process's dynamic characteristics and to develop advanced control concepts that provide high CO₂ capture efficiency in all operating conditions.

2. CO₂ emissions from steel making processes

The adoption of hydrogen-based Direct Reduced Iron (DRI) stands as a promising alternative to the traditional Blast Furnace - Basic Oxygen Furnace (BF-BOF) method, representing a significant advancement in reducing CO₂ emissions from steel production. Even natural gas-based DRI presents a more favorable environmental impact compared to conventional methods. However, the transition to DRI processes involves production units like the Electric Arc Furnace (EAF) and converters such as Argon Oxygen Decarburization (AOD), which brings forth new challenges, as these methods become the primary melting routes for steel. EAF is currently the predominant route for recycled steel and represents 23% of global steel production with specific emissions between 0.2-0.5 tons of CO₂ per ton of steel. It is anticipated that by 2050, the EAF's market share will expand, driven by both increased recycling efforts and augmented DRI production.

The treatment of off-gases from EAFs and AODs poses significant challenges for conventional CO₂ capture technologies due to their highly variable nature. These gases are intermittent and dynamic, containing a high concentration of small particles and pollutants such as sulfur and chlorine components. Moreover, the gas exhibits both oxidizing and reducing properties, complicating its handling and imposing stringent demands on the material properties of potential gas-cleaning systems.

Many EAF and AOD systems currently incorporate suction-operated hoods positioned above the furnace, designed to draw all emitted gases into a gas duct. However, these hoods typically remain open to the atmosphere, allowing for the intake of false air. While this setup facilitates post-combustion of residual CO and H₂ and results in rapid gas cooling, it poses challenges from a CO₂ capture perspective by diluting the CO₂ concentration. Current gas treatment methods for EAF and AOD off-gases primarily involve thermal recovery mechanisms, such as steam production or pre-heating of solid material fed into the furnace, followed by dust removal.

For the effective implementation of a suitable CO₂ capture system to treat variable off-gases, especially those emitted by EAF and AOD processes, a comprehensive understanding of gas behavior is essential. This understanding facilitates the accurate adaption of models to typical

off-gas parameters. Figure 1 illustrates the CO₂ concentration profile, flow rate and temperature of EAF off-gases, while a corresponding depiction for AOD off-gases is provided in Figure 2.

Figure 1. CO₂-concentration, flow rate and temperature of an AOD converter.

Figure 2. CO₂-concentration, flow rate and temperature of an EAF.

3. CaL pilot facility

SFW together with SWERIM is designing a first-of-a-kind CaL pilot facility to be integrated into the steel mill using EAF and AOD technology. The pilot facility will be located in Luleå, Sweden and is targeted to handle up to 250 nm³/s of metallurgical gas including max. 10.5% of CO₂. The facility is under detailed engineering. Commissioning and testing activities are scheduled to be started in 2025.

The CaL test facility utilizes two interconnected Circulating Fluidized Bed (CFB) reactors, the carbonator and the calciner (Figure 3). Both reactor systems consist of typical CFB components and are designed based on proven commercial-scale CFB hot loop guidelines providing robust and flexible operation with various operating conditions and full scalability from pilot to commercial scale. In the carbonator, adjustable water-cooled bayonet tubes are used for the reactor temperature control according to testing needs. Heating of the calciner is provided via air combustion mode with gas (propane) which can be fed into the reactor optionally at different elevations. The test facility will be equipped with a comprehensive set of measuring ports for temperatures, pressures, and gas compositions as well as specific sampling ports for various solid materials. Key design parameters of the pilot facility are presented in Table 1.

To achieve best CO₂ capture throughout the dynamic changes in the flue gas, the CaL test facility will include sorbent storage system and controllable wall seals. As for the controllable wall seals, those will be adopted in the return leg of both calciner and carbonator. In such wall seals, fluidizing gas is used to control the material flow between the loop seal main and bypass lines. i.e., the internal and external material flow between reactors. This is expected to provide optimal dual reactor operation even in fast transient situations.

Further, the flue gas feeding line into the carbonator will be equipped with an additional feeding system to simulate different scenarios of flue gas dust content and composition coming along with steel making exhaust gases.

Figure 3. CaL pilot facility.

Table 1. Technical data of carbonator and calciner.

	Carbonator	Calciner
Reactor inner diameter (m)	0,32	0,37
Reactor height (m)	10,0	10,0
Design Temperature (°C)	650	900
Gas analysis at the reactor outlet	O ₂ , CO ₂ , CO, NO _x , SO ₂ , H ₂ O	O ₂ , CO ₂ , CO, NO _x , SO ₂ , H ₂ O
Temperature and pressure measurements	At different reactor elevations, the reactor outlet and wall seal	At different reactor elevations, the reactor outlet and wall seal

4. Model investigation

4.1 Dynamic model

A time-dependent 1.5D simulation tool (Figure 4) was used to characterize the dynamics of the CaL process and to evaluate the effect of fluctuating flue gas properties on the operation of the CaL process. The simulation tool includes reactor models discretized into 1D control volumes, including mixing due to wall layer flow. The model includes time-dependent mass and energy balances, as well as the necessary closure equations for CFB hydrodynamics, heat transfer, and homogeneous and heterogeneous reactions [4]. Utilizing published test data [5], the simulation tool has been validated in the suitable operational range.

Figure 4. 1-D dynamic model frame for the calcium looping process [6].

4.2 Simulations and discussion

A model-based investigation of the process was performed for a pilot-scale CaL device [3] with reactor heights of 15 m, and carbonator and calciner diameters of 0.65 m and 0.75 m, respectively. Fluctuating flue gas flow from the steel process was simulated by varying the properties of the gas flow entering the carbonator between air and flue gas. The time series of the change is shown in Figure 5, and the feed properties are in Table 2. The simulation case is started by feeding air to the carbonator, and after 10 minutes, the conditions are linearly changed to flue gas within 1 minute, which is kept constant for 10 minutes. During the next 20 minutes, the conditions are linearly changed back to the air, and at the end, another 40-minute period is simulated using air. Fuel feeding, makeup flow of fresh limestone and air primary gas feed were kept constant, corresponding to the values of 1.7MW_{th} input, 0.022 kg/s and 0.5 kg/s, respectively.

Figure 5. Time-series for the carbonator feed.

Table 2. Properties of air and flue gas feed to the carbonator.

	Feed [kg/s]	O ₂ [m-%]	N ₂ [m-%]	CO ₂ [m-%]	H ₂ O [m-%]	T [°C]
Air	0.54	20.0	69.0	0.0	11.0	100
Flue gas	0.54	6.3	72.7	10.0	11.0	100 - 350

The simulated carbonator outlet temperatures versus time are shown in Figure 6a. The results show significant changes in temperature levels which are caused by the increased inlet gas temperature and by the carbonation reaction heat. Too high temperature weakens lime reaction rates as the conditions deteriorate in relation to the reaction equilibrium of the carbonation reaction (Figure 6b). The higher is the carbonator temperature increase the lower remains the CaCO₃ content of the bed material entering to the calciner (Figure 6c), indicating relative decrease in CO₂ capture efficiency. These simulations show the requirement to find ways to prevent the carbonator temperature from rising as the CO₂ concentration and temperature of the flue gas stream increase.

Figure 6. a) Carbonator exit temperatures, b) Lime reaction rates in the Carbonator and c) Bed material CaCO₃ content entering the calciner.

The storage system combined with the controllable wall seals bring extra flexibility for the CFB-CAL process. With these solutions, the reactor operations can be partially decoupled meaning that the calciner system (including ASU and CPU) can be dimensioned for the smaller capacity and hence the CAPEX and OPEX of the overall CaL system can be reduced [7]. Further, the calciner operation is not disturbed drastically during fast transients on the carbonator side which makes the calciner control easier. The CaL process provides good options for the calciner temperature control by the fuel feed, as well as by using the possible recycling of solids through internal circulation via controllable wall seals.

5. Conclusions

Dynamics simulations done in this work indicates that the intermittent steel mill gases have remarkable effects on the carbonator behavior. The CFB-CaL process with novel solutions has superior dynamic flexibility and hence it will have good potential for the carbon capture from fluctuating exhaust gases. Dynamic performance of the CaL process will be further studied by dynamic simulations as well as demonstrated in a first of a kind pilot facility which is under designing and will be commissioned during 2025. Obtained data from the process simulations combined with test data from the pilot will provide a sound basis for the scale-up of the CaL technology for the decarbonization of the steel industry.

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